

CONSTITUTION THE FOUNDATION OF OUR HAPPINESS

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Annotation: our Constitution is an important basis for strengthening our independence, and ensuring the peaceful and prosperous life of our people. The meeting, round table, open dialogue, and other cultural and educational events are highly effective in order to widely promote its role and importance in our lives, strengthening the sense of loyalty to the motherland, and respect for our laws in the minds of the population, especially young people.

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The main law was passed on December 8, 1992, in the Supreme Council of the Republic. The Constitution establishes democratic principles for the development of the state and society. During the democratic changes taking place in the Republic, changes have also been made to the Constitution.

Almost all the states that exist on Earth today have their own free politics, language, and state symbols. But not all of them have their own constitution. It is certainly our happiness that our country also has the Constitution mentioned among the national symbols. The Constitution of our state, which combines the noblest wishes and great dreams of the centuries-old Armenians of our great ancestors, the establishment of a free life, a prosperous society, and a just state, serves as a solid foundation and guideline for all acceptable laws and regulations.

It can be said with pride and pride that all reforms carried out in our country are directly based on the principle of mastery of the law. The path to equality and Justice has opened up in society. Law is a means of exercising the power of the people, managing society, and regulating social relations between the state and citizens. Hence, both the weapon, the defense, The Shield, and the eye of the legal state are the law. Such high, noble goals can be achieved by cultivating the legal consciousness of young people, forming their legal culture, and cultivating them in the spirit of respect for the law. After all, as the president noted: "the perfect generation should admire the world not only with the foundation of the development of Uzbekistan, the economy of Uzbekistan, which has developed at a high level in the future but also with educated, spiritually mature children." Bold actions towards the construction of a legal democratic state of our state can be seen in the person of reforms carried out in order to improve the activities of

the legislative body(Parliament). A new system is in operation, consisting of the legislative chamber(lower house) and the Senate (upper house). When it comes to Kezi, it is worth saying that in the preparation of laws, based on centuries-old national legal heritage and our values, it was taken into account, comprehensively studying and taking into account the legal experiences of developed democracies at the level of generally recognized rules of international law. In life, there are such concepts as well-being, and freedom. It is worth saying with pride that in the process of preparing laws aimed at ensuring the well-being of life and the freedom of citizens both in society and in society, a path of true oriental Uzbek creativity was formed, having studied foreign experience.

It serves as an important factor in ensuring the perfection of our country and the supremacy of laws, the regulation of social life, and the orientation of their activities in all aspects of society toward Great Goals. Independence means that the rule of justice is to achieve the provision of all equally equal obedience to the law. It was during the independence that the national legal mechanisms of legislation and lawmaking were created. The world view of the population increasing the level of legal and political knowledge, the consciousness of the constant pursuit of spiritual and moral perfection self-control, and control of each citizen is necessary to ensure and perceive the all-time viability of the principles of social justice. As it is the foundation of other laws in the country, the Constitution is the Basic Law of the state. The concepts outlined in the Constitution are so significant that no person can live without them because the problem that a person faces everyday solution also often depends on the rules and substances included in the main law of the country. The Constitution is to go on a fascinating journey through the Basic Law of our country, which is to know the provisions of its law. Although is a much more ancient document, he is endowed with so much knowledge and wisdom that the content is comparable to the whole universe. The Constitution, when translated from Latin, means “rules” or “charter”.

Expanding the role and function of law in the entire system of government, turning the subordinate living into a lifestyle of the population is the qualitative manifestation of a Democratic state, an incomparable advantage of civil society. “The law will be freedom in the dominant place,” as our grandfather, Amir Timur, noted. If people follow the established taste rules, their affairs are solved fairly, and freedom and a healthy legal environment are formed in society.

In our general constitution, universal values and the most important norms of international law in the constitutions of the present time are embodied. It is especially worth noting the fact that a person, his rights, and freedoms are recognized as a value in oil. Based on our national values and traditions of Uzbekistan, a separate chapter XIV of the Constitution is devoted to family issues. Indeed, an important place of upbringing, which ensures the eternity of life, the duration, and the perfection of generations, preserving our national traditions and passing them on to future generations, is undoubtedly the family. In Article 64 of the chapter "family" of our archpriest, the following words are written:" parents are obliged to feed and raise their children until they reach adulthood." Every child born in our country, until he grows up, must certainly grow and mature in the bosom of the parents. The life-giving and humanistic nature of our Constitution is that together with the desire to guarantee the good living and work of people raising children, pays special attention to the fact that the main task at their disposal is the state protection of the rights of their children. Maintaining a family, which is the main unit of society, and ensuring the maturation of children is the responsibility of humanity and the citizenship of every citizen living in this society.

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